

Ionophoretic study on complexation reactions of manganese⁻, iron⁻, cobalt⁻ and nickel(II) with *o*-methoxybenzoic acid and nitrilotriacetic acid

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Ternary complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with *o*-methoxybenzoic acid as primary ligand (HL) and nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) as secondary ligand (HA) at pH 8.5 ($\mu = 0.1 M$) and their binary complexes at different pH have been investigated by ionophoretic technique at 35°. The stability constants ($\log K_{MLA}^{ML}$) for the formation of mixed ligand complexes of the above metals with HL and HA have been evaluated.

Stepwise reactions of transition metal ions with coordinating ligands have been studied ionophoretically¹. The device is well established in the field of binary mononuclear complexes and it has been extended to the study of the ternary complexes² as well. The present work deals with the binary and ternary complexes of bivalent Mn, Fe, Co and Ni formed with *o*-methoxybenzoic acid and nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA). The stability constants of the complexes have been determined.

Results and Discussion

Metal-*o*-methoxybenzoate systems : The variations in overall ionophoretic mobility of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} (M) with the change of pH are shown in Fig. 1. There are two plateaus in each case. The first plateau at low pH,

Fig. 1. Plots of overall mobility (U) of metal ion against pH at 35°, $\mu = 0.1 M$ in metal-*o*-methoxybenzoate system

where the concentration of undissociated HL species is maximum, represents the region of uncomplexed metal ion. The second plateau, where the metal ion mobility is decreased as a result of complexation with anionic species (L) of HL, represents the formation of ML complex. The region between these two plateaus corresponds to progressive conversion of uncomplexed metal ion into binary complex ML with the ligand L species as in eqn. (1). As the mobility of all metal ions remained constant at higher pH, the possibility of formation of higher mononuclear complexes of type ML_n ($n > 2$) is ruled out.

The overall mobility of the metal ion is given by eqn. (2),

$$U = \frac{U_M + U_c K_{ML}^M [L]}{1 + K_{ML}^M [L]} \quad (2)$$

where, U_M and U_c represent mobility of M and ML respectively. K_{ML}^M , the stability of ML complex can be expressed as

$$K_{ML}^M = \frac{[ML]}{[M][L]}$$

By applying the principle of average mobility, K_{ML}^M can be calculated with the help of mobilities of first and second plateaus in Fig. 1. The values of [L] at a given pH are calculated by substituting the acid dissociation constant (K_a) of HL ($pK_a, 3.90$)³ in the eqn.,

$$[L] = \frac{[L]_T}{1 + K_a[H^+]}$$

where, $[L]_T$ is the total ligand concentration. Substituting the values of U_M , U_c and [L] in eqn. (2), the values of K_{ML}^M for the formation of ML are calculated and tabulated in Table 1.

The formation constants for the formation of binary complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II} and Co^{II} with *o*-methoxybenzoic

acid have not been studied earlier. But the logarithmic value of stability constant of Ni^{II}-*o*-methoxybenzoic acid complexes have been reported earlier⁴. The results obtained in the present investigation are not fairly consistent with the reported value of 0.8 at 25°⁴. This perhaps is due to difference in experimental conditions and limitations of the technique.

Table 1. Stability constants of binary and ternary complexes

Metal ion	log K _{ML} ^M	log K _{MA} ^M	log K _{MLA} ^M
Ni ^{II}	5.00	10.65	8.03
Co ^{II}	4.91	10.60	7.98
Fe ^{II}	4.76	10.55	7.88
Mn ^{II}	4.66	10.45	7.80

Metal-NTA systems : The plots of pH versus overall mobility of metal spots in the presence of NTA (pK_a = 9.65)⁵ show two plateaus. The negative mobility of the second plateau (Fig. 2) indicates the negative charge on the resulting complex. It is assumed that only one mole of NTA (HA) combines with one mole of metal ion giving MA complex as reported earlier⁶. The values of formation constants (log K_{MA}^M) (Table 1) are calculated from eqn. (3),

Binary complexes of NTA with divalent Ni, Co, Fe and Mn have been studied. The experimental results are nearly consistent with the values 11.26, 10.61, 8.84 and 7.44 for Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{II} and Mn^{II}-NTA complexes reported in the literature⁶.

Fig. 2. Plots of overall mobility (*U*) of metal ion against pH at 35°, μ = 0.1 M in metal-NTA system.

Metal-NTA-*o*-methoxybenzoate systems : Ionophoresis of the formation reactions of ternary complexes was carried out at pH 8.5, since the *o*-methoxybenzoate complexes (ML) are formed below it. The transformation of ML into MLA was studied here to avoid all other possible side-reactions by varying the concentration of A in the background electrolyte.

The plots of *U* vs -log [NTA] are shown in Fig. 3. The curves show two plateaus. The constant mobility in the first

plateau corresponds to the mobility of 1 : 1 ML. The mobility of the metal ion at the second plateau corresponds to the formation of MA as in eqn. (4) or the formation of mixed ligand complex MLA as in eqn. (5),

It may be noted that the observed mobilities in the second plateau are negative due to large negative charge on the resulting complexes and they do not coincide with the mobilities corresponding to the formation of ML seen in Fig. 1. This implies that the mobility in the last plateau is due to the ligation of anionic A to ML to give MLA as in

Fig. 3. Plots of overall mobility (*U*) of metal ion against -log [NTA] at 35°, μ = 0.1 M in metal-NTA-*o*-methoxybenzoate system.

eqn. (5). The stability constants corresponding to the equilibria are calculated by the eqn.,

where, K_a is the dissociation constant of HA, and [HA]_T the total concentration of HA.

The data thus obtained are depicted in Table 1. The stability constants are found to decrease in the order : Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Fe^{II} > Mn^{II}, which is in accordance with the values reported earlier⁷ and the Irving-Williams order⁸

Experimental

Ionophoretic chamber (manual) consisting of two PVC moulded tanks with platinum electrodes was employed for ionophoresis. Voltage stabilizer cum D.C. convertor (manual) was used to pass a direct current of 200 V under the complexation reactions. A SICO-EMI M-EM5 pH meter having a combined electrode was used.

Procedure : Stock solutions of 5 M HNO₃, 2 M NaOH and *o*-methoxybenzoic acid (HL, 10 mM; Kemphasol), nitrilotriacetic acid (HA, 10 mM; E. Merck) were prepared. Metal salt (Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} nitrate) solutions were prepared for spotting the paper strips used in the ionophoresis. In this procedure, the metal sulphate was treated with sodium carbonate solution followed by nitric

acid to give the required metal ion solution which was standardised by usual methods⁹. A solution of HNO₃ (0.1 M) containing HL or HA (1 mM) at a desired pH was used as background electrolyte for investigating the binary complexes. A solution of HNO₃ (0.1 M) containing HA (10 mM) and HL (10 mM) at pH 8.5 was used for evaluating the ternary complexes.

The paper strip was marked in duplicate with the metal ion; along with a few additional strips were also marked with glucose. A current at 200 V was passed through these strips initially for 15 min and continued for another 60 min after wetting them with background solution. A solution of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) indicator was sprayed to detect the metal spots and the movement of each spot was measured. The above experiments were repeated with the background electrolyte after adjusting the pH to a desired value and the metal ion mobilities determined.

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